

Summary of biosphere discussion at the ISSI workshop ‘Tipping Points and Understanding EO data needs for a Tipping Element Model Intercomparison Project (TipMIP)’, October 10 - 14, 2022

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Many of the relevant impacts of climate change on nature and society are mediated by the biosphere. Even though rising temperatures are the most immediate effect of ongoing greenhouse gas emissions, it is the emissions’ secondary effects, for example through the increased frequency of extreme weather events on food and water security, and biodiversity, that are most threatening to humanity and life on earth (IPCC, IPBES). Ecosystems, and global and local food systems embedded within the biosphere are complex systems of many interacting species and human actors that may exhibit tipping points. Climate change may be an important driver of such transitions with potentially dire consequences for nature and society.

Tipping elements typically considered for the terrestrial biosphere are the Amazon rainforest, boreal forest, as well as Sahel/West-African monsoon (Lenton, 2020; Brovkin et al., 2021; McKay et al., 2022). Boreal/tundra permafrost thaw can be also accounted as a tipping element of the biosphere from a cryosphere perspective, due to microbial decomposition of soil organic matter associated with permafrost thaw. Tipping in lakes and freshwater systems is also a concern for the terrestrial domain. These ecosystems act as reactors for greenhouse gas production, and their transition from carbon sinks to sources could create significant climate feedback loops.

Abrupt permafrost thaw (tipping element with regional impact) has been identified as one of the tipping elements with a threshold of less than 2°C global mean temperature increase (McKay et al., 2022). Abrupt thaw monitoring with EO can be achieved through observation of surface proxies. Identification of relevant features such as thaw lake extent change needs to consider actual timing

of events, facilitated through e.g. fusion of optical and radar for gap filling. Water/lake color monitoring can provide indicators for lateral transport of carbon released due to thaw.

In general, the role of freshwater-related processes and impacts for the key tipping elements needs to be clarified for permafrost and forest environments. Local tipping within freshwater ecosystems, especially lakes can play an important role in local and regional climate regulation (Balsamo et al., 2012), with potential destabilizing positive and stabilizing negative feedbacks within the climate system. There is a need for higher level/advanced EO products (for example refined lake surface water temperature products, inclusion of smaller lakes) to support investigations of lake stratification and lake phenology.

General consensus was found on the importance of extreme events and their changes for tipping within the biosphere, given their potential wide-ranging impacts from feedbacks within the climate system to biodiversity loss or economic and social destabilization. This includes heatwaves, droughts and fires, potentially in regions currently overlooked as tipping hotspots, but known to be or expected to undergo rapid change due to global warming (Seneviratne et al., 2012, 2021). For example, the pace of change of heat and drought events in the mid-latitudes and other regions results in surprising high-impact events that might suggest an ongoing destabilization of ecosystems adapted to past climate (Hartmann et al., 2022; Hammond et al., 2022). Compound events where “the combination of multiple drivers and/or hazards contributes to societal or environmental risk” (Zscheischler et al., 2018) might not necessarily be extreme in order to induce strong impacts. Still rare spatial or temporal compound events have been shown to affect ecosystem resilience (Kornhuber et al., 2019; Bastos et al., 2021).

The discussion of Earth Observation (EO) indicators for ecosystem resilience should be driven by user needs and suitability of existing data. Biomass is deemed a good proxy (structure/water content, canopy). Red-edge information can be an indicator of vegetation vitality (health). Specifically hyperspectral information is expected to advance the capability of EO for early warning in the tipping point context. Existing resilience indicators may, however, still have too high uncertainties for their use in early warning systems. This happens because (satellite) monitoring programs and (the mathematical theory of) proxies of resilience were developed largely independent of each other. A more integrated approach could help address issues arising from trends, seasonality, and data gaps in time series obtained through EO. Differences across vegetation types and the challenges to map vegetation composition should be considered. Uncertainties and quality measures of products as well as synergies between different datasets should be developed. Suitable statistical resilience indicators and caveats associated with EO data (e.g. change of uncertainties over time) need to be identified. For example, disturbance rates and their changes can be used as proxy for risks for

ecosystem resilience.

In general, vegetation-related EO products which are of high relevance for resilience of several biosphere tipping elements are missing from the ESA CCI portfolio (as well as GCOS Essential Climate Variables - ECVs), this includes

- Tree coverage / fraction – important for shifts in vegetation state
- Canopy properties (leaf area, pigment content)
- Vegetation height (not only for trees)
- Vegetation moisture content / status for resilience and vegetation heat stress
- Change in land use and land management
- Vegetation type (dominant species and diversity)

A specific topic of interest in the boreal zone is also the change in fire regimes and recovery. A challenge in the context of fires is that remote sensing proxies differ from variables in modelling, but at least burned area, fire emissions and biomass from EO can be used to benchmark models.

Other issues to be considered include delayed impacts, teleconnections and societal impacts which can have consequences at global scale. A major strength of EO in this regard is the capability to capture multiple scales, from local to regional and global tipping. Climate modelling for the biosphere needs to address the appropriate scale (spatial resolution).

Opportunities may arise from new datasets, which have, however, the drawback of short temporal coverage. When data is limited by short temporal coverage, space for time substitution might be useful to derive information about vegetation resilience. The methodological focus needs to be on shift detection and consideration of cascading tipping and threshold effects. Multivariate indicators may, in this regard, be useful because they can (in theory) obtain more information from short time series by combining information from different sources (i.e. variables) and portray the diversity of processes affecting vegetation resilience (water stress, chlorophyll and pigment content, structural changes, compositional changes etc.). More integration of ECVs and potentially EBVs (essential biodiversity variables) and platforms could therefore contribute for improved EO detection of resilience changes and tipping events.

Direct human disturbances and their feedbacks are a major issue to be addressed. In the past, the focus of tipping point and irreversibility research has been on intact systems (Claussen and Brovkin, 2009; Hirota et al., 2011; Verbesselt et al., 2016; Abis and Brovkin, 2017). However, there is increasing evidence that human influence on the landscape has the potential to reduce the resilience of ecosystems to environmental stressors (Staal et al., 2020; Nunes et al., 2022) and to impact disturbance trends (Rosan et al., 2022). Challenges include the small spatial scales at which forest degradation takes place and the fact that early warning signals might be difficult to detect. Nevertheless, the expanding capabilities in higher spatial and spectral resolution EO and in data

sciences hold great promise for such developments (Hansen et al., 2013; Zarco-Tejada et al., 2018; Brandt and Stolle, 2020; Boulton et al., 2022). Solutions need to be found to account for anthropogenic drivers when using process-based models as well as EO. Considered disturbances are not only expressed in land-use/land cover change but also include land management such as irrigation as can be potentially inferred from combination with soil moisture EO products. These effects are not currently considered in models used to assess tipping points, making this a domain where EO can have a valuable contribution to advance model and scenario development

Final remarks The biosphere is not only a key part of the climate system, it is also a key provider of ecosystem services for human well-being and life on Earth. Biospheric tipping elements and tipping points are, therefore, of strong significance for policymakers and impact assessments. Impacts may depend on the areas and/or sub-spheres affected by climate change (for example on whether they are biodiversity hot spots or provide key ecosystem services). Therefore, it is crucial to not only assess tipping elements in terms of their importance for the climate system, but to consider their significance for life on Earth and the essential services they provide as well. Recent advances in EO facilitate the analysis of extreme events, ecosystem resilience, and the potential threat of permafrost thaw on a much finer scale than before. Cascading impacts and compound events in the Earth System are now easier to quantify for evaluation of Earth System models applied for future projections. We should use this opportunity now.

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